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ABSTRACTS

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Catabolism of monolignols by pseudomonads

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Abstract: Agriculture worldwide generates significant quantities of lignocellulosic biomass (LBM) that can become source of energy and materials. LBM comprises of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. While cellulose and hemicellulose, have been maximally exploited to produce fuels and chemicals, lignin is relegated to meet the power demands. Depolymerization of lignin by chemical catalysis yields a heterogenous stream of aromatic molecules, however separation to obtain a single molecule is laborious. Opting for biological route to valorize such streams is environmentally benign. While fungi have been maximally studied for degradation of lignin, they exhibit multiple bottlenecks which may become an impediment during commercialization. Bacteria are noteworthy for their catabolic potential of monolignols. In the current study, two well-known strains of *Pseudomonas* namely *Pseudomonas putida* KT440 and *Pseudomonas putida* S12 along with a *Pseudomonad* isolated from a soil were studied for growth and metabolic profile on monolignols as sole carbon source. All three strains exhibited different behaviour when grown on aromatic monomers derived from lignin singly or in concoctions. The findings of this work have paved a way for valorization of lignin to products of commercial importance.

Keywords: Lignocellulosic biomass, lignin, Pseudomonads, valorization.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

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